

A holistic tool to assess the cost and environmental performance of floating offshore wind farms

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ABSTRACT

Since the beginning of the transition from onshore to offshore wind power, there has been a sustained trend to move the turbines farther away from the shoreline, which needs the use of floating substructures. It entails constant efforts to overcome technical, environmental and economic challenges to construct a more sustainable wind power technology, being able to provide the growing energy demand that our society is facing. This study shows a holistic tool based on systematic and comprehensive methodologies to evaluate the economic aspects and environmental impacts of the life cycle of floating offshore wind farms. The characteristics of those farms can be defined by the user to create study scenarios, introducing input data as well as using updated existing data stored in the tool library. A monolithic concrete spar platform technology for 15MW offshore turbines located in two sites is used as a study case (10 km off the coast of Gran Canaria - Spain and 60 km off the coast of Morro Bay - California), to generate six scenarios with different wind farm capacities ranging 60MW to 1200MW. The production, installation, operation and maintenance, decommissioning and End-of-Life recycling stages are considered in the structure of the tool to give overall and broken-down results by stages, components and materials. This allows identifying the environmental and economic hotspots, driving the decision-makers and engineers towards a sustainable floating wind technology and enhancing cost reduction strategies to boost this technology in the current energy transition scenario, which is underway around the world. When compared to a model created by specialized LCA software that meets the same specifications and criteria, the tool is robust enough to deliver reliable results, with deviations of roughly 6%. The outcomes of the scenarios investigated framed in the novel concrete-based platform are promising; since LCOE values range from 67 to 115 €/MWh and GHG emissions between 7 and 10 kgCO₂ eq./MWh, with uncertainties of ±9% and ±22% respectively.

KEYWORDS

Offshore Wind Energy
Floating Concrete Platform
Levelised Cost of Energy (LCOE)
Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)
Key economic and environmental parameters

1 INTRODUCTION

Currently, energy generation is one of the economic drivers in the world, however, the depletion of conventional fossil fuels, along with the increase in the energy demand and environmental implications, entails challenges in achieving a sustainable and growing society. Under this premise, wind turbines have a leading role, since today there is 743 GW of wind power capacity worldwide, helping to avoid over 1.1 billion tonnes of CO₂ globally (1). In 2020, the total installed wind energy capacity was around 210GW in Europe, equivalent to supplying 14% of electricity demand. By 2030 it could reach 350GW, supplying up to 24% of electricity demand (2). Offshore wind power is emerging as a key growth area in the energy transition contributing to such wind power capacity. Fixed-bottom technology is the type of base structure dominant in the offshore wind market; however, this technology is only suitable for water depths below 50m (3). This limit can be overcome by using floating platforms which technology needs further maturity. This approach makes it possible to convert offshore wind energy to larger areas where the water depth ranges between 50m and 200m. The further from the coast the floating turbine plants, the winds are stronger and more consistent, and more energy output would be had with these higher wind speeds, fewer species of birds can be harmed by the spinning blades. In addition, the wind farms would create fewer conflicts with fishermen and other users of the oceans and they can be out of sight from the shore. Another benefit of this technology is that it allows for future cost savings because wind turbines are constructed in port before being towed to the site and connected to the mooring system (4).

By 2020, alone in Europe has the largest floating wind energy capacity in the world accounting for over 70% of the total (2). This included Hywind Demo (2.3MW), SeaTwirl S1 (0.3MW), Hywind Scotland (30MW), Floatgen (2MW), Kincardine Pilot (2MW), the Windfloat Atlantic Phase 1 (25.2MW), and the 50 MW Kincardine floating offshore wind farm that is now fully operational (5). Since then, the capacity was expected to be significantly increased in the next three years with the installation of projects in the UK, France, Norway and Portugal, ranging between 24MW to 88MW (6). With these ranges and considering an increased rated power of the turbine, higher than the one installed in those days (around 10MW), a first short-term scenario was defined with higher capacity than the average size of the European offshore wind farms in operation, which was 200MW by the end of 2019. However, this capacity was strongly exceeded by 30GW in 2020 and the global forecast indicates an additional growth of up to 15GW by 2030 (7). Nevertheless, to achieve this target, there still are technical economic and environmental challenges to positioning the floating substructures in the offshore wind power market.

The cost evaluation of bottom-fixed offshore wind has been the focus of several studies, such as the one carried out by Mark and Brian (8) who developed an empirical model for offshore wind installation cost calculation of a bottom-up approach in the U.S. Outer Continental Shelf. Results showed a cost range of \$130,000 to \$370,000 per MW and they weren't relatively sensitive to the distance to the port, but they show a decline as the turbine capacity increases, while the cost of installation increases with the time required for installation. These costs can be lower than the floating wind power technology depending on the distance to the shore. Although the main motivation for moving towards offshore energy is the minimal impact on human life, land resource and especially fossil fuels avoiding; the economic perspectives are counterbalanced by the higher capital, installation, and maintenance costs (9).

Levelized cost of energy LCOE is another and the most common approach used to evaluate the feasibility of wind power generation. The calculation of LCOE is based on all costs over the project's life cycle (also called Life Cycle Costing (LCC)); levelled to the energy generated

during the lifetime of the energy generation system. The LCC analysis concept was early introduced by the U.S. Department of Defense (DoD) in the 1970s, being still used currently by a wide variety of projects involved in a range of industry sectors, for instance, construction, energy, transport, manufacturing and healthcare. LCC analysis is defined as a process of evaluating the economic performance of a system or a project over its entire life span (10). The main usefulness of the LCC methodology is identifying, analysing, evaluating and reduction of overall operation key costs.

The results from LCOE analysis in the context of renewable energies are used to enhance the strategies of managers and engineers regarding the economic life of project assets, comparing the cost performance concerning conventional energy source technologies and providing the stakeholders in making appropriate investment decisions. Christoph et al. (11) used this methodology to compare the levelized cost of electricity of renewable energy technologies for electricity generation with conventional power plants in Germany. Authors also estimated the future cost ratio between the different power generation technologies for the years 2030 and 2040. Their findings revealed that the LCOE of offshore wind power projects is dropping like a stone. With up to 4500 full load hours, offshore wind power plants achieve electricity production costs between 72€/MWh and 120€/MWh. The specific plant costs are between 3000 and 4000€/kW, including the connection to the mainland. Offshore wind power plants still have a strong cost reduction potential compared to onshore wind power plants. The LCOE is expected to drop to values between 5896€/MWh and 96€/MWh, depending on location and wind supply.

Specifically for conceptual floating wind technology, a comprehensive analysis and comparison of LCOE of offshore floating wind farms was conducted by Myhr et al. (12): five platforms concepts made up of 100 MW turbines (Spar-Buoy (Hywind II), Tension-Leg-Spar (SWAY), Semi-Submersible (WindFloat), Tension-Leg-Wind-Turbine (TLWT) and Tension-Leg-Buoy (TLB)). Their results showed floating turbines for increasing depths generally experience increased LCOE at a lower rate than bottom-fixed turbines. The optimum site was established at 100km offshore, which would provide LCOE in the range of €82.0/MWh - €236.7/MWh for the conceptual designs analysed. Recently, Tyler and Patrick (13) performed a wind energy cost review which presents a snapshot of the levelized cost of land-based, offshore, and distributed wind energy, using empirically derived and modelled data representative of 2020 market conditions. Their results revealed the cost of these wind energy technologies varies regionally across the United States and other parts of the world. These results are also found in other studies, thereby, it can be stated that the LCOE is inherently related to specific projects at specific locations.

On the other hand, in environmental terms, offshore wind power technology is expected to have low levels of resource consumption and few pollutant emissions during the operation stage (i.e., during the generation of electricity). However, stages of the life cycle (e.g., manufacturing and end-of-life) are worth being assessed to know their environmental impacts. The life cycle assessment (LCA) methodology is used to evaluate the environmental performance, which is supported by the ISO 14040/44:2006 (14,15). This methodology allows for a comprehensive evaluation of the potential environmental impacts associated with all stages of the wind energy life cycle, from cradle to grave. A multi-criteria analysis based on the LCA tool has been applied majority to fixed-bottom offshore wind technologies. Several authors have conducted these analyses, such as Birkeland (16), Bonou et al (17) and Huang et al. (18) while floating systems have not been addressed enough.

A low number of published LCA studies are found to evaluate the environmental performance of floating offshore wind systems. To cite a few of them, Pujol et al (19) analysed the environmental performance of a floating pilot offshore wind farm based on a detailed inventory built upon primary data and a geo-located electricity estimation model. Some materials, in particular steel, are reported to contribute largely to the floating platform production and turbine. Floating technology was also included in the LCA of offshore farms when considering the effects of locational factors, depth, and distance from shore (20), where the farm system, with 20 fixed and floating offshore commercial wind farms installed in the Great Lakes surrounding Michigan, showed acceptable results respect other wind platform technologies. Another author is Weinzettel et al (21), who did an LCA of the offshore turbine in 2009 and Jesuina et al (22) who conducted an LCA of onshore and offshore turbine farms recently in 2018.

All of these authors reported several environmental different categories such as abiotic depletion, global warming, human ecotoxicity, freshwater ecotoxicity, and terrestrial ecotoxicity included in the Institute of Environmental Sciences (CML) 2 baseline 2000 V2.03 method (23), including Cumulative Energy Demand (CED) (24). As an example, each of these studies reported kgCO₂ eq. emissions referred to different functional units (1kWh or MJ of energy produced) for a time scale of 20 years; the values go from 7.3 to 41.4gCO₂ eq/kWh. This wide range is due to different considerations used by authors and specific objectives of their studies focused on turbine power rate (3 MW – 6MW) generating different capacities of the wind farms (5 MWh – 300MWh). Moreover, their methods (except Pujol et al. (19)) do not describe how electricity production is modelled. In addition, as in most of the previously presented studies, the considered life cycle inventories (LCIs) are average inventories based on existing databases rather than being directly fed by a specific supplier's data.

Under this context, COREWIND is a European project that is providing cost-effective solutions for floating offshore wind technology, leading to low costs by developing innovative research, modelling and optimization for concrete-based floating substructure concepts (25). This article is framed on this project, where a holistic tool to assess the cost and environmental performance of floating offshore wind farms has been developed. The holistic tool (named onwards FowApp) is presented. It gives the decision-makers and engineers insights in floating offshore wind farms, from both an environmentally sustainable viewpoint and economic perspective, which aims to boost this technology to have a further significant role in the energy transition that the world is undergoing. To show the potential of FowApp, farms having concrete-based floating platforms to support 15MW turbines are used for two different locations.

FowApp includes the LCOE and LCA methodology following the system boundaries from the raw material extraction, component manufacturing, installation of the farm, operating and maintenance (O&M), decommissioning and end-of-life (EoL). This latter is defined as a suitable scenario that includes proportions of materials to landfill, incineration and recycling according to the nature of materials entering the production stage, unless the components are sold, reused or left onsite. In addition, the energy payback time (EPBT), energy return on investment (EROI) and carbon payback time parameters are calculated by FowApp to describe the energy generation and emissions performance of the wind power farms. Fowapp was developed due to a lack of software that integrated a detailed definition and calculation of a complete floating windfarm. In this regard, no other software was developed to compute the LCA of offshore wind farms, while the LCOE tools existing in the market lacked accurate energy calculations (i.e., considering wakes and power flows) and/or the possibility of introducing a detailed cost breakdown of the complete wind farm lifecycle.

2 METHODOLOGY

The environmental and economic assessment is conducted through FowApp which is a tool developed under a holistic approach consisting of two modules for each evaluation topic. Such an approach follows the life cycle structures of LCA and LCOE methodologies considering the production of wind farm components, installation, O&M, decommissioning and EoL stages. Four parameters are taken into account, namely, Capital Expenditure (CAPEX), Operational Expenditure (OPEX), Decommissioning Expenditure (DECEX) and Annual Energy Production (AEP) to know the levelised costs of the energy produced during the useful life of the floating wind farm, specially focused on platform technology, mooring system and O&M activities. The environmental assessment model follows the LCA guidelines established by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) 14040/44 family of standards (14,15). Both the cost model and environmental model are described in detail in section 2.2 and 2.3 respectively. The integration of both methodologies in FowApp allows for to evaluation of as many scenarios and floating offshore wind technologies by using data stored available in its library and/or introduced by the user.

Specifications for study are defined in the following subsections, which include the type of substructure, turbine capacity, locations and scenarios, as well as the structure and operating principle of FowApp.

2.1 Floating wind farm description

Several scenarios subjected to different definitions of parameters and aspects are defined in FowApp to establish the code of the tool as flexible as possible. These aspects are described in the next sections.

2.1.1 Turbine specifications

FowApp is structured in such a way that specifications of any turbine can be introduced for calculations. In this study, a 15 MW reference wind turbine is used. The turbine is the IEA 15MW defined by NREL with HAWC2¹ implementation by DTU. Its official definition was already published in March 2020 to serve as an open benchmark that is defined with publicly available design parameters to be used as a baseline for studies (26). The overall parameters of this turbine are shown detailed in (26).

2.1.2 Floating platform technology

Floating offshore wind concepts emerge as a need to locate new installations further out, and in deeper waters. At depths ranging from approximately 40m to 60m, the cost of bottom-fixed and floating wind substructures are comparable, but at depths greater than around 60m, installing bottom-fixed foundations is not economically feasible and technically challenging (27), therefore, better and more economical solutions must be developed to meet this challenge.

The platform considered in this study is based on the spar-buoy concept (WindCrete) being evaluated for cost reduction in the COREWIND European project. Its basic design is described in (28). This substructure consists basically of a monolithic concrete spar platform including both the tower and the floater in a unique concrete member. The use of this monolithic characteristic allows to drive out weak points since joints between the tower and the floater are avoided. The whole structure is in a compression state by the use of active reinforcement, and it is designed to avoid traction at any point during the life span of the platform (28). The advantages and disadvantages of this concept are summarised in Table 1.

¹ HAWC2 is an aeroelastic code intended for calculating wind turbine response in time domain (<https://www.hawc2.dk/>)

2.1.3 Locations

The potential wind farm sites considered for this platform concept are described as follows and shown in

Figure 1 and Figure 2.

- Gran Canaria Island, Canary Islands (Spain), 200-meter depth. Distance to shore: 10km. Sandy soil.
- Morro Bay, California (USA), 870-meter depth. Distance to shore: 60km. Sandy soil.

Figure 1 Gran Canaria site.

Figure 2 Morro Bay site.

The characteristics of these locations are summarized in (28) and are taken into account in FowApp. The app will be as flexible as possible to provide accurate results and conclusions based on the selected sites. Both the depth and the characteristics of the seabed are assumed to be the same at each site, therefore varying from site to site but not inside them, for practical analysis. This consideration will reduce the complexity of the later layout optimizations and allow generic conclusions.

Table 1. Advantages and disadvantages of the Spar-buoy concepts (29).

Spar-buoy concept	Advantages	Disadvantages
<p data-bbox="323 981 501 1014">WindCrete (28).</p>	<p data-bbox="651 577 997 1003">A relatively simple design for which production is highly scalable, giving potential cost savings through serial fabrication. The design has reduced maintenance requirements as the structure encompasses fewer moving parts, due to the absence of an active ballast system. Due to the deep draft and comparatively lightweight top section, the system has excellent stability and buoyancy.</p>	<p data-bbox="1042 577 1390 1003">The large draft constrains deployment in shallow waters and also limits the structure's ability to be towed back to port to undergo maintenance. Furthermore, this requires that the structure be towed out to the deployment area where it will be installed. This requires specialist equipment such as heavy lift cranes and other dynamic positioning vessels, thus increasing deployment cost and risk.</p>

2.1.4 Farm capacity

Both LCOE and LCA calculations are referred to the same unit, which is defined as 1MWh of electricity produced during the lifetime. Consequently, the capacity in terms of MW of the floating wind farm should be defined. As mentioned above, according to a Wind Europe report (6), Europe's floating wind fleet is the largest worldwide (70%) with a total of 45MW installed by the end of 2019 and the capacity is expected to be significantly increased in the next three years ranging between 24MW to 88MW (6). With these ranges and considering the rated power of the turbine in this project (15 MW), a first short-term scenario is defined with a capacity of 60MW (4 turbines).

However, most of the deployed offshore wind farms are based on bottom-fixed turbines. They are located in shallow waters (<30m) and close to shore (<30km), generally in less challenging environmental conditions than those found further offshore (29). The average size of commercial wind farms has been almost doubled over a decade from 313MW in 2010 to 621MW in 2019, although significant increases were achieved in 2011, 2017, 2018 and 2019 (6). The average size of the European offshore wind farms in operation by the end of 2019 was 200MW, but if non-commercial farms were not considered, the figure would increase. On the other hand, with the growth of installed bottom-fixed capacity, future installations will need to be located further out and in deeper waters (27,30), where the floating technology is likely to be the only choice. Based on this and the mentioned capacity ranges and references, a second scenario is defined with 300MW (20 turbines).

Reduction of floating technology costs is expected and a potential factor to achieve them is the economies of scale. Furthermore, that behaviour is expected by the offshore wind market and already happened with the bottom-fixed technology. Two examples are East Anglia (714MW) and Hornsea One (1,218MW), the largest offshore wind farms already supplying electricity to

the grid (6). This is why a FOWF scenario in the long-term scenario is also defined with 1200MW (80 turbines).

2.1.5 Layout

In the reference layouts, the platforms are linearly arranged to form a rectangular matrix. This approach will allow a practical calculations and establish a baseline for further work for all scenarios, the separation is set to 7 rotor diameters (1680m), a rule that is considered general practice; in these scenarios, the mooring requirements are less restrictive. A generic wind farm layout is proposed for each wind farm capacity defined, with a distance between rows and columns as per the previous paragraph. Consequently, the initial layouts are site-independent except for the West of Morro Bay site with WindCrete substructures and are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Generic wind farm layouts associated with reference wind farm capacities (rows are perpendicular to prevailing wind direction).

Reference capacity	Number of turbines	Number of rows	Number of columns
60MW	4	1	4
300MW	20	4	5
1200MW	80	8	10

Both the regular matrix arrangement and separation are subjected to change after an optimisation process (not included in this study) depending on costs, refined (and less restrictive) mooring requirements and wind distribution. It is expected the evolution experienced by the arrangement of the first (bottom-fixed) offshore wind farms, which was a line or regular layout: the recent wind farms are often characterized by a more erratic layout as a consequence of their optimisation (31).

2.1.6 Electrical system and substations

According to the details provided by developers, the choice of the configuration for the grid connection to shore is subjected to the wind farm capacity, the distance to shore and the associated costs. The export cables of Southeast of Gran Canaria wind farms would be shorter than 25km, therefore HVAC is considered for any wind farm size in both sites. On the other hand, the Morro Bay site is located further (around 60km), therefore HVAC is considered but the HVDC approach may also be analysed for the 1200MW farm.

Regarding substations, for the 4-turbine farms, offshore substations would represent a high relative cost compared to the wind farm cost. Moreover, the distance to shore is not very high for any site. For that reason, it appears to be more realistic to assess these farms without offshore substations, connecting the turbines directly to the onshore substation. For the 20-turbine farms, a 300 MW substation may represent a smaller relative cost, therefore it could be considered for Barra and Morro Bay site.

The distance to shore in Gran Canaria is relatively small, and the strings may be directly connected to the onshore substation. Five strings of 4 turbines would ensure a clean cable layout.

In the case of the 80-turbine farms, two 600 MW offshore substations should be considered for all scenarios, as their high power justifies their placement regardless of the distance to shore. In this case, 16 strings (8 per substation) of 5 turbines each would also ensure a clean and consistent cable layout.

2.1.7 Study scenarios

The characteristics defined in previous subsections are grouped in 6 study scenarios (Table 3) that be evaluated using FowApp.

Table 3. Reference scenarios for the LCOE and LCA assessment.

Scenario	Location	Separation	Capacity	Grid connection configuration
4W			60MW 4WT	Single string to the onshore substation
5W	SE of Gran Canaria	7D	300MW 20WT	5 strings the to the onshore substation
6W			1200MW 80WT	16 total strings to 2 offshore substations, plus export cables to the onshore substation
7W			60MW 4WT	Single ring to the onshore substation
8W	W of Morro Bay	9D	300MW 20WT	5 strings to the onshore substation
9W			1200MW 80WT	16 total strings to 2 offshore substations, plus export cables to the shore substation

W: WindCrete, 7D & 9D: rotor diameters of separation, WT: Wind Turbine

It is worth noting that the IEA 15 MW reference wind turbine will be used in all scenarios. The scenarios are referenced by an arbitrary number and a letter, which identifies the substructure technology (WindCrete). The wind farm layout (relative turbine positions) of scenarios depends on the wind farm capacity according to Table 2 and A 66 kV HVAC inter-array grid is considered for all scenarios.

2.2 Cost evaluation model

Several approaches can be applied to offshore LCOE calculations having a significant impact on results. Some of them include cash flow analyses (32) and adapted formulas (33), physical depreciation over the lifetime or tax depreciation dictated by federal policy (34), and even some include policy incentives expressed in real and nominal currency (35,36), among others. This LCOE study considers the physical characteristics of the plant, useful for comparing different technologies, with economic assumptions such as depreciation over the life of the plant and no capital structure apart from the discount rate. This LCOE is made to provide an average, it does not reveal the revenues required to finance a project using a particular technology.

As mentioned above, parameters in the model are CAPEX, Operation and Maintenance Cost (O&M - OPEX), DECEX and AEP. The FowApp tool calculates the LCOE based on the NPV method (37) and assumes decommissioning costs correspond to the first year after the farm has stopped its production. The LCOE is then calculated using Eq. 1.

$$LCOE = \frac{CAPEX + \sum_{y=1}^n \frac{OPEX_y}{(1+i)^y} + \frac{DECEX}{(1+i)^{n+1}}}{AEP \cdot \sum_{y=1}^n \frac{1}{(1+i)^y}} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

LCOE is the levelised cost of energy in €/MWh, CAPEX is the capital expenditure, OPEX_y is the operational expenditure of the year *y* and DECEX is the decommissioning expenditure, all of them in €. AEP is the annual energy production in MWh and *i* and *n* are the discount rate and the project lifetime respectively.

2.2.1 General considerations of the LCOE calculations

The costs associated with the CAPEX are described as follows:

- Development of the project, defined as per one of the following options:
 - As a percentage of manufacturing + construction costs.
 - As detailed costs.
- Manufacturing of the turbines, towers, substructures, moorings, anchors, cabling and substations.
 - Turbine, tower, anchor and substation costs are determined based on their price and quantity.
 - Cabling and mooring costs are determined based on their price and total lengths.
 - Substructure costs are calculated as the sum of labour, procurement, light equipment, area leasing and heavy equipment costs associated with their manufacturing.
- Construction of the wind farm, as the costs derived from the usage of auxiliary means, i.e., heavy equipment, land transport, vessels and air transport. Additionally, expenses such as area leasing, labour and light equipment may be included.

The costs associated with OPEX are:

- Operation costs, defined as per one of the following options:
 - Annual operation cost.
 - Sum of specific costs (e.g., management, licencing, insurance, etc.).
- Maintenance costs as the sum of procurement, area leasing, labour, light equipment and auxiliary means cost associated with each predictive or corrective maintenance activity.

The costs associated with DECEX are:

- Pre-decommissioning expenses.
- Decommissioning of the wind farm, as the costs derived from the usage of auxiliary means, i.e., heavy equipment, land transport, vessels and air transport. Additionally, expenses such as area leasing, labour and light equipment may be included.
- Final treatment of the wind farm components (e.g., incineration charges, landfill charges, etc.) or income derived from the sale or reuse of the components.

2.3 Environmental assessment model

The LCA follows 4 steps that are iterative, namely (i) Goal and Scope (ii) Life Cycle Inventory (iii) Impact Assessment and (iv) Interpretation. The potential impacts that are generated along the life-cycle stages can be analysed to identify environmental hotspots providing useful information for further improvements in the design, production, performance and disposal stages, to reduce the impacts on the environment. These steps are included in FowApp to assess the environmental implications of the floating offshore wind farm technology aligned to the life cycle cost approach described in previous sections for the LCOE calculation. A general scheme showing the structure of the FowApp LCA module is in Figure 3.

Figure 3 General scheme of LCA module (top) and interface screenshots showing the inputs and outputs of the FowApp model (bottom).

2.3.1 Goal and Scope

The goal and scope of the LCA are inherent to FowApp objectives and they are to provide an environmental assessment of floating offshore wind technology. Since there are a considerable number of scenarios to be developed in detail in this study, scenario 5W is used as a study example. The scope follows the broadest approach suggested by the ISO 14040 for a comprehensive and holistic LCA; Cradle-to-Grave from the production of wind farm components, installation, O&M, decommissioning and EoL stages of scenarios defined in Table 3. This approach allows insight into those components/sub-components or sub-processes responsible for the highest environmental impacts. This gives the tool the characteristic to identify environmental hotspots, which will help to reduce the impacts and to improve the wind farm performance.

2.3.2 Life Cycle Inventory (LCI)

The inventory analysis quantifies materials and energy consumption and environmental emissions based on the study scope and boundaries previously established for the different scenarios (see Figure 4). Quantities and information (foreground data) were obtained from experts involved in the project. Background data for the upstream processes were based on

recognized datasets from EcoInvent and GaBi Professional databases. A summary of the WindCrete technology (scenario 5W) LCI is shown as follows in the next subsections:

Figure 4 System boundary for LCA of WindCrete solution in FowApp

Materials for wind farm components

Table 4 shows the percentage of aggregated materials corresponding to the components and sub-components of the wind farm. The WindCrete foundation represents around 95% of the total weight of the system wind farm (scenario 5W) being the ballast made by-products from the electrical furnace, which avoids the consumption of virgin materials.

Table 4 List of main materials considered in the component manufacturing for WindCrete farm (Gran Canaria site – 300MWh)

Component	Material	Percentage (%)
Cables-CW002 66 kV HVAC submarine cable- dynamic Inter-array (Core <<conductor and screen wires>>, armour insulation system, sheathing)	Copper	1
	Steel	
	High-Density Cross-linked Polyethylene (XLPE)	
	High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE)	
Foundation + Tower (Bottom hemisphere, cylinder buoy, tapered transition piece and ballast)	Concrete	95
	Passive steel	
	Active Steel	

	Ballast (Black slag, by-product of electrical furnace with a density of 2500 kg/m ³)	
Mooring system (Mooring lines (chain R3), links(R4S), connector and anchor)	Hot rolled steel	1
Turbine (20 turbines) Rotor: Blade, Hub, including pitch servos and bearings Nacelle: Tapered double outer shaft bearing ring, spherical roller shaft bearing Turret, Turret flange, bedplate yaw system, including bearing Drivetrain: Generator stator, generator rotor and shaft	Glass fibre reinforced	3
	Carbon fibre	
	Resin	
	Steel, low alloyed	
	Copper	
	Cast iron	
	Magnet (Neodymium)	
Life span (year)	Turbine	25
	WINDCRETE foundation + tower	60
	Cables-CW002 66 kV HVAC	25
	Mooring system	25

Transportation model

Different kinds of transportation are included in the LCA FowApp model can be the whole life cycle of the FOWF used for all scenarios. These transportation types are related to the main activities involved in the installation, O&M and decommissioning stages, which are summarised in Table 5.

Table 5 Transportations within the FowApp life cycle structure of the offshore wind farm

Transportation description	Input parameters	Type of transportation and auxiliary means	Default considerations
Raw material transportation from the supplier to the manufacturing facility	Distance, km Weight of material, kg	Lorry Freight ship Transoceanic freight ship	Transport from a local supplier: 50km Transport from European supplier: 2000km Transport from rest of world supplier: 8000km
The road transport of wind farm components and parts for pre-assembly at the port and decommissioning up to the waste management facility	Road distance, km Weight of material, kg Number of trucks	Trucks	---
All transportations to prepare loads to vessel at the port, sail to site offshore and installation at site offshore, maintenance and	Operating time, h Fuel consumption, l/100km Fuel hourly consumption, l/h Fuel type	Trucks Vessels: barges, tugboats, crane vessels, jack-up vessels, excavators, cable laying vessels, etc.	$FC = \frac{EC \cdot P \cdot 3600}{\left(\frac{\eta}{100}\right) \cdot t \cdot \rho}$

decommissioning (sailing to port).	Fuel density, kg/l Power specific fuel consumption, kg/MWh
FC is the fuel hourly consumption, l/h	
P is the rated main engine power, MW	
η is the engine efficiency, %	
EC is the power specific fuel consumption, kg/MWh	
ρ is the density of the selected fuel, kg/l	
t is the duration of the trip in hours, h	

Energy generated

The energy generated by the wind farm is a key parameter to meet the goal of the study and the functional unit defined above. Both LCOE and LCA require the lifetime energy generated (LEG), for which, the AEP was calculated, former equal to the AEP multiplied by the wind farm lifetime (25years). The AEP is considered as the energy delivered to the onshore grid, i.e., the energy output of the wind farm's onshore substation.

The following aspects or steps were taken into account in the calculation model to get the AEP:

- Geo-located wind resource assessment.
- The use of the turbine's power curve model to calculate the annual ideal mechanical energy, also allows the calculation of the wake losses.
- The annual mechanical energy calculation.

Table 6 Main production energy concepts and losses

Electrical energy delivered (AEP) broken down	Losses included
Ideal energy production	Wake loss
Mechanical energy production	Wind turbine electrical loss and electrical grid loss
Electrical energy production	Downtime loss

Figure 5 Balance of the energy generated

Other considerations are also taken into account, such as the turbine internal losses associated with the mechanical/electrical transformation and internal cabling (electrical efficiency of 96.5% to get a maximum output of 15.0MW) and a 95% factor is applied to calculate the energy output due to the wind farm downtime.

In general terms, the energy production concepts and losses considered in the FowApp model are listed in Table 6 and the energy balance is shown in Figure 5.

Decommissioning and EoL

Decommissioning is assumed to be a reverse process of installation (20). After the dismantling and sorting of the decommissioned specific components, materials can be destined for different EoL processes or scenarios. For this FowApp version, the EoL process encompasses three scenarios, namely, landfill, incineration and recycling. Additional two feasible scenarios will be included into FowApp in the future (reuse/Sale and Leave-On-Site).

The environmental impacts associated with the dismantling and material sorting account for the fuel consumption of the vessels and auxiliary means used in this phase. To do this, the transportation and parameters such as the number, types of vessels and equipment and hours of duration of decommissioning operations are needed. On the other hand, the same quantities and types of materials specified in the component production stage are considered materials to be managed during the EoL of the FOWF.

To quantify the impact, the FowApp user can indicate the destination of these materials or components according to the EoL scenarios mentioned above. In a summarized way, the parameters on which the assessment is based are: quantities, types of materials and waste management plan or scenario for each of them.

Nevertheless, a base case scenario for the EoL by materials is included in FowApp based on the specific recycling rates of different components depending on the major material they are built from, material purity and easy dismantling. In this sense, materials or proportions, that do not allow recycling, are going to the landfill or incineration according to their characteristics. Some of them (e.g. plastics) can contain harmful chemicals that cannot be incinerated but disposed of in a landfill.

Based on the above, FowApp offers by default an EoL best-practice scenario (Table 7) using recycling, incineration, and landfilling ratios based on previous research and LCA literature (38,39,48,40–47). Any other materials obtained from the dismantling process of the wind turbine array, are assumed to be landfilled.

Table 7 EoL best-case scenario according recycling, incineration, and landfilling ratios (38,39,48,40–47).

EoL - Recycling, Landfilling and Incineration ratios (%)			
Material	Recycled	Landfilled	Incinerated (no energy recovery)
Metals: Aluminium, Copper, Steel, Iron	90	10	0
Polymers (TFE, PVC, PP, PE, Polyester, Epoxy Resin, Paint, Carbon fibre)	30	40	30
Other Plastics, Glass Fiber, Rubbers	0	0	100
Concrete	0	0	100
Slags, Magnet, silver, Wood, Glass, Brass, tin	100	0	0

EoL allocation 50-50 approach in FowApp LCA

One of the issues in LCA is how to allocate the environmental benefits of recycling, concerning the use of virgin materials, between the process being studied (process A) and another process

being out of the system boundaries (process B). Both of them are involved in the flow of secondary materials. To do this, two ‘extreme’ approaches can be found in the literature: recycled content (also named as cut off approach) and the EoL approach, but there are also options to go in between (43).

The cut-off approach takes into account secondary materials that are input to a process have zero attached environmental burden except for energy use and transport for collection, sorting, etc. Secondary materials on the output leave the product system without any further environmental (43). In the EoL approach, secondary materials that are input to a process have the same attached environmental burden as virgin materials. Here, secondary materials on the output side leave the product system causing an extra environmental burden (energy use for melting and transport for collection, sorting) as well as an environmental bonus (avoided burden virgin material production), i.e., the benefit of recycling goes entirely to the process A (47).

We have chosen a combined approach adapted from the 50-50 approach (47). The approach would divide the ‘bonus’ over the wind farm system and another process being out of the system boundaries. The recycling process (collection, sorting) is not divided being to go the wind farm system and the avoided final waste treatment is assumed to go to another process. It is worth noting that the environmental burden for the recycling process is applied as zero because of the lack of information.

2.3.3 Life cycle impact assessment (LCIA)

This phase calculates the potential for specific environmental burdens in each impact category assessed. Several impact categories can be assessed, as well as multiple characterization factor models to quantify the categories. Midpoint impact categories are considered in FowApp LCA model for the impact assessment, which can suitably represent the environmental profile of the floating wind farm according to the goal and scope definition. The impact categories assessed in this study are at the midpoint level since they reduce uncertainties associated with assessing the potential environmental damages.

These categories consider the environmental implications that are more important for the system studied, mainly associated with the energy consumption, affecting the climate change and primary energy demand, damage to the soils and ecosystems and harm to human health. On the other hand, a susceptible concern for natural resource consumption (minerals).

In this view, seven environmental categories are considered for the FowApp LCA model as follows:

Global Warming Potential (GWP), CML 2001- Jan. 2016 – kg CO₂ eq: This metric describes the emission of greenhouse gases that lead to increased radiative forcing and a raise in mean global temperature.

Abiotic Depletion Potential Elements (ADPe), CML 2001- Jan. 2016 – kg Sb eq: abiotic resources are non-living natural resources. The ADPe is a measure of the potential depletion of minerals.

Primary Energy Demand from renewables and non-renewables (PED) – MJ: PED is a measure of the potential primary energy consumption before any process, i.e., the energy available in primary or natural resources such as fossil fuel.

Acidification Potential (AP), CML 2001- Jan. 2016 – kg SO₂ eq: AP measures the increased acidity of soil and water due to proton release from anthropogenic emissions.

Eutrophication Potential (EP), CML 2001- Jan. 2016 – kg PO₄ eq: EP measures increased biomass formation and loss of biodiversity due to the release of nutrients.

Aquatic Toxicity Potential (ATP), USEtox 2.1, Ecotoxicity – CTU_e: ATP is a measure of the potential of a chemical emission to cause adverse impacts on the ecosystem.

Human Toxicity Potential (HTP), USEtox 2.1, Human Toxicity, cancer – CTU_h: HTP is a measure of the potential of a chemical emission to cause adverse impacts on humans.

To convert the inventory and to classify elementary flows by emissions, we proceed to perform a unitary life cycle assessment per kg of material to know each environmental impact in the above categories. These impacts are obtained using the GaBi software version 10.1 to generate the values of unitary LCAs incorporated into the library FowApp.

In this sense, FowApp is able to calculate the total impacts (T) for each category. Calculation examples are shown for the following categories through Eq. 2 - 3:

$$GWP_T = \sum_{i=1}^n \text{kg material}_i \cdot \text{kg CO}_2 \text{ eq per kg}_i \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$ADPe_T = \sum_{i=1}^n \text{kg material}_i \cdot \text{kg Sb eq per kg}_i \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$PED_T = \sum_{i=1}^n \text{kg material}_i \cdot \text{MJ per kg}_i \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

2.4 Assumptions and considerations for LCOE and LCA models

The results of this study are subjected to the availability and quality of data obtained from floating wind farm experts, literature and datasets. Thus, the majority of foreground data of components and materials were provided by the project experts. Assumptions and considerations are detailed as follows:

- The life span of the substructure is stated to be 50 and 60 years, however, this LCA assumes an operational lifetime of 25 years for the whole farm, which matches the current standard design life. In this sense, the credits of the substructure (due to the reuse of the concrete-based substructure) are not considered.
- Materials, which were not found in the databases were substituted with materials having similar properties, through consultation from the developers/experts and solid criteria based on the experience of the authors of this study.
- In that case, the electricity generation source used in the LCA was assumed from Europe as an EU-28 mix grid from GaBi professional database (49).
- It has been assumed that all the materials which enter the production systems, are sourced as virgin (except the slags recycled from the steelmaker sector). On the other hand, some databases from Ecoinvent or GaBi could include secondary materials. In that case, these materials would be considered to get a consistent mass balance in the EoL stage.
- In this study, when the concrete in the substructure reaches the end of its useful life, it is wasted in a landfill rather being recycled. However, the potential recycling of concrete may bring environmental benefits. This improvement will be addressed later during the optimization of the FowApp model.
- No faster wake recovery due to increased turbulence nor wake reflection is considered.
- Economies of scale are not considered.
- No AEP variations are considered for the LCOE and LCA calculations.

- Marine growth end of life is not considered.
- Recycling costs are omitted.

3 Results and discussions

3.1 Environmental performance of the floating wind farm (5W scenario)

This section addresses the LCA results of the 5W scenario by using a model performed in the commercial GaBi software following the same approach included in FowApp. This is to contrast the results to verify the reliability of environmental assessment results from FowApp.

Results from the GaBi model

Figure 6 shows the percentage contribution of life cycle stages of the Gran Canaria WindCrete scenario for all environmental impact categories considered in this study. The negative impacts associated with the EoL stage mean benefits due to the material recycling considered in the model, which contribution ranges from -11% to -42% through all impact categories. On the other hand, the manufacturing stage, including production and transportation associated, shows a higher contribution in all environmental impact categories. The installation is the next stage contributing to the environmental impacts (not as much as the manufacturing stage), in particular on the AP, GWP and PED categories (21%, 13% and 11% respectively).

Figure 6 Environmental impact percentage contribution of all the life cycle stages of the Gran Canaria WindCrete scenario

Similarly, the decommission stage shows contribution for the AP, GWP and PED categories, 20%, 14% and 13% respectively. O&M is the stage with the lower contribution to overall results. The absolute emission metrics per MWh of energy produced by life cycle stages are shown in Table 8.

Table 8 Environmental impact results per MWh produced of the Gran Canaria WindCrete scenario life cycle stages

Impact category	Manufacturing	Installation	O&M	Decommissioning	EOl	TOTAL
ADP elements (kg Sb eq/MWh)	6.12E-05	2.70E-07	1.07E-07	2.50E-07	-1.81E-05	4.37E-05
AP (kg SO ₂ eq/MWh)	3.68E-02	1.26E-02	5.15E-03	1.21E-02	-6.42E-03	6.02E-02
EP (kg PO ₄ eq/MWh)	2.66E-02	5.33E-04	3.36E-04	8.22E-04	-3.19E-03	2.51E-02
GWP (kg CO ₂ eq/MWh)	6.29E+00	9.20E-01	4.23E-01	1.01E+00	- 1.42E+00	7.23E+00
PED (MJ/MWh)	9.81E+01	1.20E+01	5.65E+00	1.34E+01	- 2.29E+01	1.06E+02
ATP (CTUe/MWh)	1.91E-01	1.28E-03	7.70E-04	1.86E-03	-2.95E-02	1.65E-01
HTP (CTUh/MWh)	4.84E-10	2.98E-12	1.61E-12	4.12E-12	-1.46E-10	3.47E-10

When focusing on the GWP category, the result is 7.23kgCO₂ eq /MWh or what is the same as 7.23gCO₂ eq/kWh. This value is aligned with results found in the LCA literature dedicated to measuring the environmental impacts of floating wind farms at pilot scale or individual floating wind turbines. Table 9 shows some GWP results of LCA studies from literature where we can see the values ranging from 7gCO₂ eq/kWh to 40gCO₂ eq/kWh. It is worth noting that the comparison of the Gran Canaria WindCrete scenario with the literature LCA results is not proper as a comparative study to say if one project is better to another one, since each author applies the LCA methodology guidelines using different criteria, goals and scope, such as the capacity of the farm, lifetime, turbine power and capacity factor. However, these literature results are indicative since they validate the order of magnitude of the Gran Canaria WindCrete scenario result.

Table 9 LCA results of some studies of offshore wind farms found in the literature

Floating wind power technology	Turbine (MW)	Farm Capacity (MW)	Time life (years)	GWP (CO₂eq/kWh)	Reference
Pilot floating offshore wind farm	6	24	20	22.3	Poujol et al (19)
Offshore Wind farm Siting	3	300	20	32.5	Tsai et al (20)
Floating offshore wind turbine	5	200	20	11.9 – 41.4	Weinzettel et al (21)
Floating offshore wind turbine in Texas	5	5	20	7.3	Chipindula et al (50)

Since the manufacturing stage is dominating the overall life cycle results, it is interesting to know which component contributes significantly to this life cycle stage. In this sense, the turbine is the component responsible for the higher contribution in all environmental categories (except in EP), as shown in Figure 7. This is attributed to the material consumption involved in the production of the turbine, being the carbon fibre with the higher contribution in almost all categories (AP, EP, GWP, PED and HTP). As an example, the contribution by the material is shown for the GWP category in Figure 8. For ADP elements, the materials contributing largely

to the turbine are glass fibre (27%), permanent magnet and steel, each of these latter around 22%.

Figure 7 Environmental impact percentage contribution of manufacturing by life cycle stages

On the other hand, the impact contribution of the resources (material and energy), involving the substructure manufacturing, revealed that steel is the material with the highest impact in almost all impact categories (more than 50% of contribution). Concrete, which is the main material used in this innovation, is the next material contributing to the results, but with a lower contribution compared to steel, such as shown for the GWP category in Figure 8, which is very similar to the ADP elements category (results are not shown here).

Figure 8 kg CO₂eq emissions percentage contribution by materials of Turbine and Substructure (scenario 5W) in the manufacturing stage of the wind farm

FowApp vs. GaBi model

The LCA results of the Gran Canaria WindCrete scenario generated from the FowApp have been compared against the results obtained using the environmental model performed in GaBi software to know the consistency of the results. The GaBi model follows the goal and scope defined previously and uses the same inputs (inventory) as the ones in the FowApp. Figure 9 shows the comparison of overall results in terms of percentage normalised to 100% for the

GaBi model. Considering all categories, it can be observed the percentage of average deviation is around 6%. In particular, for the GWP we can see a deviation of 5%.

Since manufacturing is the most relevant stage in the overall life cycle results, these differences are contributed mainly from this life cycle stage, which averaged 8%. The differences in the results of the other life cycle stages follow a similar behaviour.

Figure 9 GaBi vs FowApp overall LCA results

The origin of these differences can be also mainly found in the O&M lifecycle stage, which, as seen before, has a minor contribution to the LCA overall results. Nevertheless, they seem to affect those indicators that deal with fuel consumption (and associated emissions due to its combustion) in the use of the auxiliary means in these maintenance operations. This consideration provides some hints on the origin of these differences that point out that the cause is likely found in the frequency of the O&M operations that are undergone. FowApp uses the result of calculating the number of operations divided by the 25 years, considering that the first year is not computable, while GaBi perhaps is taking into account the number of operations considering also the first year. Another possible source of difference is the consideration of the fuel consumption of the auxiliary means in both models. Eventual issues fixing in the FowApp model have to be double-checked in GaBi in future to verify the consistency of the tool.

3.2 LCOE and LCA results of floating wind farms (All scenarios)

Table 10 shows the main characteristics of the scenarios, including their AEP and their capacity factor. For the Gran Canaria site, it can be observed that the AEP is higher in the 6W scenario concerning 9W.

Table 10. General parameters and energy production of offshore wind farm scenarios

Scenario	Site (Distance to shore)	Capacity (MW)	AEP (GWh/year)	Capacity factor (%)
4W	Gran Canaria	60	374	71.1
			374	71.1
5W	(Spain)	300	1796	68.3
			1796	68.3

6W	1200	7080	67.3
		7080	67.3
7W	60	268	50.9
		268	50.9
8W	Morro Bay (USA) (~60km)	300	47.9
		1284	48.8
9W	1200	4920	46.8
		5052	48.0

Figure 10 summarises the main results of the previous table. It can be observed that the Gran Canaria site farms have the highest average capacity factor, attributed mainly that Morro Bay site farms having the lowest average wind speed.

Figure 10 The average capacity factor of the reference scenarios grouped by site.

On the other hand, the capacity factor decreases as the wind farm capacity increase, which is due to the wake effect. This can be explained due to largest wind farms having a significant wake effect due to the array arrangement.

The economic results associated with the LCOE metric are shown in Table 11. It can be observed that the best values are obtained for site Gran Canaria site farms, which is the closest site to shore and has the highest capacity factor. While site Morro Bay site farms present lower values because it has the longest cables, the greatest depth and the weakest wind speeds.

Table 11. Main economic parameters of the reference scenarios.

Scenario	Site (Distance to shore)	LCC (M€)	CAPEX (€/MWh)	LCOE (€/MWh)
4W	Gran Canaria (Spain) (~10km)	452	2.67	67.1
5W		2241	2.65	69.6
6W		9028	2.70	71.6
7W	Morro Bay (USA)	520	3.52	115.0
8W		2597	3.52	120.4

9W	(~60km)	10114	3.35	117.9
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Environmental results focused on the GWP, PED, AP and ATP categories are listed in *Table 12*. Other parameters are also shown such as the Energy Pay Back Time (EPBT) and Energy Return on Investment (EROI). The EPBT of a power generating system is the time required to generate as much energy as is consumed during production and lifetime operation of the system (51), while the EROI parameter is the amount of energy delivered to society by technology to the total energy required to find, extract process, deliver, and otherwise upgrade that energy to a socially useful form (52).

Table 12. Main environmental parameters of the reference scenarios.

Scenario	Site (Distance to shore)	EPBT (years)	EROI	GWP (kg CO ₂ eq/MWh)	PED (MJ/MWh)	AP (kg SO ₂ eq/MWh)	ATP (CTUe/MWh)
4W	Gran	0.7	36.8	6.56	97.8	0.0478	0.1573
5W	Canaria (Spain)	0.7	35.1	6.86	102.5	0.0495	0.1637
6W	(~10km)	0.7	34.8	6.91	103.5	0.0501	0.1661
7W	Morro	1.1	23.3	9.96	154.8	0.0733	0.2209
8W	Bay (USA)	1.1	22.3	10.37	161.5	0.0762	0.2304
9W	(~60km)	1.1	22.4	10.40	161.0	0.0760	0.2340

The EPBT results show that the associated energy use ranges from 0.6 to 1.4 years (average of 1 year), which means that the lifetime energy requirements of wind farm scenarios analysed may take up to 1.4 years (as maximum) of operation, therefore, the next 23.6 years, one of these scenarios may power a lot of households without consuming electricity generated using conventional energy sources that's just important bonus. On the other hand, the EROI parameter results are in a range between 18 and 39 averaging 27. These results are aligned with the literature (52), although such comparison should be qualified since the studies found in the literature are a combination of factors, including larger wind turbines creating economies of scale, more efficient technology, greater rotor diameters increasing the load factor, and higher hub heights providing access to greater wind speeds (52).

The environmental results depend on each scenario and impact category. For example, when focusing on the categories strongly influenced by the energy consumption and the associated emissions, such as GWP, PED and AP, they show similar behaviour. As an example, Figure 11 shows the kgCO₂ eq/MWh profile for all scenarios against the distance to shore and capacity of the wind farm.

In general terms, it can be observed that this floating offshore technology has higher CO₂ eq emissions when installed in the Morro Bay site for different wind farm capacities than Gran Canaria site farms. It is attributed to the higher amount of material related to the export cables and transportation for installation/assembly and maintenance due to the largest distance to shore in the Morro Bay scenario. However, all of them are below 20gCO₂ eq/MWh, which is a promised result.

Figure 11 kg CO₂ eq /MWh of references scenarios vs. distance to shore vs. capacity

3.3 Uncertainty analysis

Numerous sources of uncertainty, primarily related to methodological choices, initial assumptions, such as allocation rules, system boundaries, and impact assessment methods, as well as the quality of accessible data, may all have an impact on the conclusions of an LCA study (53), also extended to LCOE calculations. In addition, experience has shown that inventory uncertainty can be considerable in LCA investigations (54). In this sense, as a result, an inventory-related uncertainty and characterization factor uncertainty for the different impact categories is used in this study to examine the results' robustness, especially when comparing two or more technologies or products, as the ISO14040 standard suggests.

Our model for uncertainty calculation can provide an overall uncertainty estimation for the entire inventory by using propagation error. The model is adapted from an approach used by the IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories - Annex 1: Managing Uncertainties to estimate the uncertainty associated with the full inventory of GHG emissions converted to CO₂ eq. This approach states that the uncertainty of the emissions or removals is propagated from the uncertainties of the activity data, the emission factor and other estimation parameters. To do this, estimates of the mean and standard deviation are needed for each input, as well as equations through all inputs (inventory) are combined to estimate output (55).

In our model for the LCA and LCOE result from uncertainty calculation, we firstly focus on uncertainties in inventory data and the environmental impact value level of a determined environmental impact category and monetary conversion factor. In this vein, for the LCA result, the uncertainty value for each impact category of each component *i* of each life stage of the floating wind plant is calculated. The approach involves multiplying the inventory uncertainty associated with the quantity by the uncertainty of the environmental impact value (henceforth impact value). Thus, the combined uncertainty quantity is to be combined by multiplication following the Eq.5.

$$U_{impact\ i} = \pm \sqrt{U_{Inventory\ i}^2 + U_{impact\ value\ i}^2} \quad \text{Eq.5}$$

$U_{Impact\ i}$ is the percentage of uncertainty in the product of the parameters, $U_{Inventory}$ and $U_{impact\ value\ i}$, to give the total percentage uncertainty associated with each of the parameters of *i* component.

Then, the overall uncertainty, by including all life cycle stages (manufacturing, installation, O&M and decommissioning and EoL ($U_{impact (overall)}$)), is calculated by combining for addition and subtraction through the Eq.6.

$$U_{impact (overall)} = \frac{\pm \sqrt{(U_1 \times X_1)^2 + (U_2 \times X_2)^2 + \dots + (U_n \times X_n)^2}}{|X_1 + X_2 + \dots + X_n|} \quad \text{Eq.6}$$

Where $U_{impact (overall)}$ is the percentage of uncertainty in the sum of the quantities, with a 95% of the confidence interval. X_i and U_i are the uncertain quantities and the percentage uncertainties associated with them (55).

Regarding the impact value uncertainty for the GWP impact category, we have approximated it to carbon emission factor for the global population of fossil fuel combustion sources, that is characterised as quite low (5-10%) in the IPCC methodology (55). That uncertainty is assumed at 7% for energy and industrial sectors involved in the manufacturing process, such as suggested by IPCC s (55). Authors have considered the use of the same percentage of uncertainty for the rest impact values for other categories, as a good proxy to assess the uncertainties of the results of the rest of the impact categories besides GWP, due to the lack of specific uncertainty rate suggestions for the impact categories factors. However, the practical applicability of the GWP default uncertainty values has been considered a reasonable option at this level in this study.

The uncertainty associated with inventory data was defined considering aspects associated with themselves as part of data collection procedures, they are described as follows:

- 1) Initial data from invoices, meter readings or Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) records (5%)
- 2) Initial data from partly invoices, meter readings or ERP records and partly from estimates (10%)
- 3) Data estimated from internal KPIs, generic studies, averages (20%)

Applying the overall uncertainty values to the different life cycle stages' impact category values as per Eq6, the results for the environmental impact indicators provided in table 20 are then subject to the uncertainty value that is $\pm 9\%$.

Table 13 Uncertainty values for the environmental impact categories

Data - Inventory (%)	Impact value (%)	Uncertainties (%)	
		Life cycle stages (result from Ep.5)	Combined overall uncertainty for LCA impact categories (result from Eq.6)
10-20%	7%	12-21%	9%

The assessment of the uncertainty on the LCOE calculated values has been performed similarly. In this case, the uncertainty due to the data used for the LCOE calculation has been estimated equal to 20%, while the uncertainty due to the economic factor has been assumed to be 10%. As a result of applying the uncertainty formulas (Eq.5 and Eq.6), an LCOE uncertainty value of 22.4% is obtained, which means that the given LCOE values have an uncertainty rate of $\pm 22\%$.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A reliable cost and environmental evaluation of floating offshore wind power plants can be conducted using FowApp, developed in the frame of the COREWIND European project. This tool follows holistic and comprehensive methodologies, as are LCOE and LCA. The tool was created with a flexible architecture in mind, allowing it to analyse several projects while taking into account a wide range of input characteristics and criteria to characterize each research case. To show its potentiality, the study case is defined as a monolithic concrete spar platform technology to support 15MW offshore turbines located in two locations far from shore, which allows generating six scenarios with wind farm capacities between 60MW and 1200MW.

The overall LCA results show the manufacturing stage (including transportation to the facilities) has the highest environmental impact along the categories studied. As an example, the manufacturing stage of the 5W scenario has a contribution of 86% concerning the overall CO₂ eq. emissions. In contrast, the EoL scenario, modelled by considering material proportions to landfill, incineration and recycling, revealed negative impacts (environmental benefits) due to material credits from the recycling approach. This is a measure to support the circular economy of the wind farm. Results of the EoL stage represent -20% of overall CO₂ eq. emissions. Other impact categories follow a similar behaviour with environmental benefits in the EoL up to - 40% of the overall LCA results. The consistency of these results was validated using a specialized LCA software, showing a global deviation percentage of around 6% respecting the results of the mentioned above software. This shows how robust the tool is, although improvements should be done to reduce the deviation in the future.

A single environmental impact and cost result cannot be provided encompassing all scenarios and locations analysed through FowApp, since they depend on the distance to the shore, length of cables, the capacity factor, depth and wind climate, among other parameters. However, the tool gives results and conclusions following the same methodological basis for comparative aims. Results involving the scenarios studied with uncertainty estimates are also included in this study as a plus to be implemented into FowApp. In this sense, if we focused on carbon footprint, results range from 6 kg CO₂ eq/MWh to 13kg CO₂ eq/MWh. Range values in other categories are also calculated with an estimated overall combined uncertainty of 9%. The LCOE results, considering all scenarios studied, ranged from 67€/MWh to 120 €/MWh with an uncertainty of 22%. Furthermore, FowApp provides the calculation of two valuable metrics for evaluating energy generating performance, namely the EPBT and EROI. They are both between 0.7 and 1.1 years and 22 and 34, respectively. Although such a comparison should be qualified because the studies found in the literature include a combination of factors, such as larger wind turbines creating economies of scale, different efficiency, and greater rotor diameters, among other aspects, these results are still useful as indicative values.

The aforesaid findings restate that this type of floating substructure technology for offshore wind power contributes significantly to the renewable energy transition while adhering to circular economy principles for a long-term future of offshore wind farms. FowApp provides reliable results for solid conclusions since its architecture is based on holistic and comprehensive characteristics of LCA and LCOE methodologies. The app functionality is not limited to the tasks described in this study, helping engineers to make correct decisions and identify cost-cutting hotspots for floating offshore wind power.

NOMENCLATURE

AEP	Annual Energy Production
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
CED	Cumulative Energy Demand
DECEX	Decommissioning Expenditure
EoL	End of Life
FowApp	Floating Offshore Wind Assessment app
FOWF	Floating Offshore Wind Farm
FU	Functional Unit
GHG	Greenhouse gas
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Cost
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Energy
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
WT	Wind Turbine

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